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SKILLS

**Report on collected fMRI
data related to effects of
intensity of ICT use on
brain activity associated
with attention and with
linguistic and
mathematical processes**

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Report on collected fMRI data related to effects of intensity of ICT use on brain activity associated with attention and with linguistic and mathematical processes

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Executive summary

Associations of adolescents' information and communication technology (ICT) skills and activities, measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire, and their brain activity, measured with functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), and task performance in mathematical tasks in the presence or absence of distracting speech were studied in 189 12–14-year-old Finnish participants. The results showed no associations of ICT skills or activities with the participants' performance in the mathematical tasks. There was only one association of ICT skills with brain activity: Participants' higher content creation and production skills were associated with stronger fMRI responses from the parietal white matter. However, this finding is suspicious, because reliability and functional significance of fMRI findings in the white matter are not clearly established.

A subgroup of Finnish participants ($n = 60$) also performed listening and reading tasks during fMRI. In these tasks spoken or written sentences were to be classified as semantically congruent (e.g., “This morning I ate a bowl of cereal”) or incongruent (e.g., “This morning I ate a bowl of shoes”) at the presence or absence of distractor sentences in the other modality, that is, written distractors during the listening task and spoken distractor during the reading task. Performance accuracy in these tasks increased gradually with the amount of online gaming in participants' daily life, suggesting that gaming may be advantageous for development of linguistic or attention skills, or both, needed in the present fast-paced tasks. However, performance accuracy dropped for participants gaming excessively (“several times a day” or “almost all the time”), suggesting that detrimental effects of excessive gaming override the positive effects of gaming on cognitive skills. Moreover, participants' communication and interaction skills, as well as their content creation and production skills, had an interaction with Task (reading vs. listening), and Distractor (present vs. absent) which might be interpreted as negative associations of these ICT skills and linguistic skills. Perhaps the participants had acquired high ICT skills at the expense of linguistic skills. There was also one unexpected significant association of ICT skills and brain activity during the linguistic tasks: Higher information, navigation, and processing skills were associated with higher activity in the anterior insula of the left hemisphere. Previous studies have suggested that this brain area is involved in linguistic processing and therefore also this finding suggests an association of participants ICT and linguistic skills. However, since there was no association of the information, navigation, and processing skills with task performance, it is not possible to interpret whether positive association of these skills and activity in the left insula reflects higher processing efficiency or higher effort during linguistic task performance.

Finally, associations between adolescents' ICT skills and activities and their attention and working memory skills measured with widely used cognitive tasks in 51 12–13-year-old Belgian participants were investigated. The results showed that participants with lower attention skills had higher amounts of online activities and were sharing more on social media. However, the causal direction is not possible to resolve from this cross-sectional data: Either adolescents with lower attention skills are prone to online and social media activities, or the amount of time spent online and in social media is detrimental to adolescents' attention skills. Moreover, participants performing worse in the working memory task had higher self-reported communication and interaction skills, but again causal direction of this association cannot be resolved here. A subgroup of 19 participants also completed the ySKILLS performance test that measured their digital skills in practice. Performance on this test was positively correlated with participants' working memory capacity. Participants with higher working memory capacity showed higher performance on the performance tests. This suggests that high working memory capacity is advantageous for development of ICT skills or that developing high ICT skills may be accompanied by development of working memory skills, or both.

In conclusion, the present studies found some associations of ICT skills and activities with performance and brain activity during linguistic tasks, as well as with attention and working memory skills. However, given that the present data are cross-sectional, no strong causal implications can be drawn from these data.

1 Introduction

1.1 The ySKILLS project

The ySKILLS (Youth Skills) project is funded by the European Union (EU's) Horizon 2020 programme. It involves 16 partners from 13 countries to enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the information and communications technology (ICT) environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for children and young people by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills. Starting from the view that children are **active agents in their own development**, ySKILLS examines how digital skills mediate the risks and opportunities related to ICT use by 12–17-year-olds in Europe (see <https://yskills.eu>).

The overarching aim of ySKILLS

To enhance and maximise the long-term positive impact of the ICT environment on multiple aspects of wellbeing for all children by stimulating resilience through the enhancement of digital skills.

ySKILLS will **identify the actors and factors** that undermine or can promote **children's wellbeing** in a digital age. The relations between ICT use and wellbeing will be critically and empirically examined over time.

ySKILLS' research objectives

To acquire extensive knowledge and better measurement of digital skills.

To develop and test an innovative, evidence-based explanatory and foresight model predicting the complex impacts of ICT use and digital skills on children's cognitive, physical, psychological and social wellbeing.

To explain how at-risk children (as regards their mental health, ethnic or cultural origin, socioeconomic status and gender) can benefit from online opportunities despite their risk factors (material, social, psychological).

To generate insightful evidence-based recommendations and strategies for key stakeholder groups in order to promote European children's digital skills and wellbeing.

This report contributes to achieving the second objective of ySKILLS by focusing on how ICT skills and activities impact children's cognitive functions. More specifically, this report presents the results from functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) experiments conducted in Finland and related experiments conducted in Belgium in Task 5.5 of the ySKILLS project.

ySKILLS has proposed, and will continue to develop, its **conceptual model** (see Figure 1):

1.2 This report

This report presents the results from Task 4.5 aiming to elucidate associations of ICT skills and activities on adolescents' cognitive and brain functions in attention-demanding tasks. To this end, fMRI and task performance data were collected in two countries: Belgium and Finland. In this report, we present the results from these studies. This presentation will be preceded by a description of the background, aims, and methods of these studies. However, these descriptions will be brief, as detailed information on these issues was already included in the previous report:

Salmela-Aro K., Alho, K., Järvinen, J., Salonen, V., Mannerström, R., Hietajärvi, L., Maksniemi, E., Puukko, K., Gale, J., Bossens, E., Ylinen, A., Wikman, P., Bellon, E., & De Smedt, B. (2022). *Report on the effects of ICT use on attention-related cognitive functions measured with ESM and fMRI. Focus on ESM and fMRI methods to measure effects of ICT skills and use on wellbeing and cognitive functions*. KU Leuven: ySKILLS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7733627>

2 Background

2.1 ICT use and cognitive skills

The ways people use ICT may affect their cognitive functions and the related brain functions. For example, studies in adolescents and young adults have shown that frequent video gaming may enhance attention and working memory skills, whereas frequent multitasking may deteriorate these skills and enhance distractibility by task-irrelevant information (for a review, see Alho et al., 2022). In one such fMRI study (Moisala et al., 2017), brain activity and performance of adolescent and young adult participants was measured during an audio-visual working-memory task with spoken and written memory items (vowels). Those participants who played video games more frequently were faster and more accurate in their task performance. They also showed higher prefrontal brain activity presumably associated with enhanced control of attention and maintenance of items in working memory. Another fMRI study (Moisala et al., 2016) examined an overlapping group of participants and found that those who multitasked (e.g., texted while watching a video or listened to music during reading) more frequently in their daily life were more distractible and showed higher distraction-related right prefrontal brain activity. In this study, the participants' task was to classify written or spoken sentences as semantically congruent (e.g., "This morning I ate a bowl of cereal") or incongruent (e.g., "This morning I ate a bowl of shoes"), and to press the respective response button (see also Moisala et al., 2015). Higher distractibility of more frequent multitaskers was indicated by a diminished number of correct responses when they classified written sentences at the presence of unrelated spoken distractor sentences or music and when they classified spoken sentences at the presence of unrelated written distractor sentences.

In both afore-mentioned fMRI studies, performance, distractibility, and related brain activity were studied in linguistic task settings. Recently, we developed a paradigm to study brain activity during arithmetic task performance at the presence and absence of distracting task-irrelevant speech (Ylinen et al., 2022). Mathematical tasks are also well-suited to study effects of ICT use on cognitive functions, since attention and working memory are critical and strong determinants of performance in mathematical tasks (De Smedt, 2022; Spiegel et al., 2021), and as noted above, these skills may be affected positively or negatively by different types of ICT use (Alho et al., 2022). Moreover, Pagani et al. (2016) studied over 1400 Italian high-school students and found that the students with better self-reported digital skills received higher scores in national tests in mathematics, as well as in national reading tests. Sanbonmatsu et al. (2013), in turn, observed in a group of over 300 adult participants that higher amounts of daily multitasking were associated with worse performance in a dual-tasking test where the participants simultaneously solved mathematical problems and maintained a set of numbers in their working memory.

2.2 Aims of the current research

The aim of the fMRI experiments conducted in Finland was to study associations between adolescents' ICT skills and activities measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire (Helsper et al., 2022) and their task performance and brain activity in closed and open mathematical tasks (McMullen, 2016) at the presence or absence of distracting speech in a paradigm developed by Ylinen et al. (2022). Moreover, in a subgroup of participants, we studied associations of the participants' ICT skills and activities and their performance and brain activity in linguistic tasks where the participants judged the congruency/incongruency of written or spoken sentences at the presence or absence of distracting spoken or written sentences, respectively, in a paradigm developed and used by Moisala et al. (2015, 2016).

The aim of the behavioral experiments conducted in Belgium was to determine associations between adolescents' ICT skills and activities and their attention and working memory skills measured with the widely applied Flanker task (Eriksen & Eriksen, 1974) and n-back task (e.g., Pelegrina et al., 2015), respectively. In a subgroup of participants, the associations between their ICT skills measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire, their performance measured with the ySKILLS performance test (Helsper et al., 2022), and their attention and working memory skills were additionally examined.

3 Methodology

In this section, we describe the methods only to the extent needed for understanding the results reported here. For further methodological details, see our previous report (Salmela-Aro et al., 2022).

3.1 Participants

In Finland, fMRI and ySKILLS questionnaire data were successfully collected from 189 participants (87 males and 102 females). They were 12–14 years old (mean 13.3 yrs.). All of them participated in fMRI conditions with mathematical tasks and 60 of them (30 males and 30 females; age range 13–14 yrs., mean 14.3 yrs.) performed also subsequent linguistic tasks during fMRI. All participants were volunteers recruited from the schools of the greater Helsinki area. All of them had achieved an average or higher grade (7 or higher on a scale from 4 to 10) in school mathematics in the last grading. This inclusion criterion was used, as participants with lower mathematical skills were expected not to be able to perform fluently the experimental arithmetic tasks, a prerequisite for reliably imaging brain activity associated with arithmetic task performance. All participants were native Finnish speakers with self-reported right-handedness, normal hearing, and normal or corrected-to-normal vision, and with no self-reported history of neurological or psychiatric disorders. All participants and their legal guardians gave written informed consent to participate. The experimental protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital District of Helsinki and Uusimaa, Finland (HUS/3322/2017).

In Belgium, the Flanker task, n-back task, and ySKILLS questionnaire data were collected from 51 12–13-year-olds (20 males, 31 females), who all were in their first year of secondary school. Nineteen of them (8 males, 11 females) also completed the ySKILLS performance test that measured their digital skills (Helsper et al., 2022). All participants and their legal guardians gave written informed consent to participate. The study was approved by the Social and Societal Ethics Committee of the KU Leuven, Belgium (G-2020-2901). All data in Belgium were collected online due to COVID-related restrictions.

3.2 Procedures

3.2.1 ICT skills and use

All participants completed the ySKILLS questionnaire (Helsper et al., 2020). This questionnaire taps into four dimensions of ICT skills and use: (1) technical and operational skills, (2) information, navigation, and processing skills, (3) communication and interaction skills, (4) content creation and production skills, and as well as participants' confidence in ICT use and the amount of their online activities, and their knowledge about ICT. In the Finnish sample, we focused on the following online activities: (1) Social media use (questionnaire item COM1), (2) overall internet use (item INT1), (3) online learning (items ACT1a, ACT1b and ACT1c combined), and (4) online gaming (item ACT1h).

A subsample of the Belgian participants ($n = 19$) also performed a performance test to measure their ICT skills (Helsper et al., 2020). The test consisted of a series of tasks in which the participants had to search for information online, had to be critical towards online conversations and had to create online content. This test was executed online during a conversation with the researcher. The participants' responses were coded according to the coding scheme of Helsper et al. (2020).

3.2.2 Mathematical tasks

fMRI data were collected at the Advanced Magnetic Resonance Imaging Centre, Aalto University, Espoo, Finland. The mathematical fMRI experiment included three tasks (Figure 2), used also by Ylinen et al. (2022). In the Solve task, the participants solved arithmetic calculations shown on one side of a computer screen projected onto a mirror mounted on the head coil of the MRI scanner. The equations included both simple calculations with only one arithmetic operation (e.g., '3 + 4', '10 : 5') and complex calculations with two arithmetic operations (e.g., '5 + 1 * 3'). A portion of calculations also included parentheses (e.g., '9 : (5 - 2)'). To solve the equations, the participants were to pick up digits (from 0 to 9) on the other side of the screen by clicking them with a computer cursor (e.g., for '5 + 1 * 3=', they were to choose '1' and '5' in this order to create the number 15). In the Create task (McMullen et al., 2016), the participants were given a target answer and a set of numbers and operators from which their task was to construct equations resulting in the given answer. In the Select task, the participants were presented with number symbols and in some cases also parentheses, and their task was to select the corresponding symbols. There were one, two, three or five numbers (e.g., '2 6 3 7 1') or three numbers and parentheses (e.g., '8 (3 2)'). The Select task was designed to control for visual and motor activity during the Solve and Create tasks. The participants performed the tasks in a self-paced manner in 1-minute blocks using a trackball to move a cursor and click on the symbols on the screen. They could erase their answer by clicking 'Remove' button and when they were finished with a task line, they clicked 'Next' button, and the next line appeared.

Figure 2. Mathematical tasks during fMRI

Screen shots from different conditions of the fMRI experiments are shown. In the Solve task, the participants solved calculations shown on one side of a computer screen (randomly on the left or right) and picked up numbers for their answer from the other side of the screen by clicking them with a cursor (+) controlled by them with a trackball. In the Create task, the participants were shown a target answer and a set of numbers and operators from which they constructed equations resulting in the given answer. In the Select task, the participants were presented with numeric symbols, and in some cases also parentheses, and their task was to pick up the corresponding symbols. The participants could erase their answer by clicking the 'Remove' button. When they were finished with a line, they clicked the 'Next' button, and the next line appeared. In the actual experiment, all texts on the screen were in written in Finnish.

Two types of task-irrelevant auditory stimulations were delivered via headphones during the tasks. These were either dialogues between a girl and boy with classroom babble in the background or incomprehensible noise-vocoded versions (only three frequency bands) of the same dialogues and babble (cf. Davis & Johnsrude, 2003). The dialogue+babble distractor was designed to mimic distracting classroom voices, whereas its noise-vocoded counterpart was used to create a less distracting meaningless stream of noise with the same audio-spectral features as in the dialogue+babble distractor.

During fMRI, there were altogether 24 1-minute task blocks, eight for each task and half of them including the dialogue-babble distractor, and the other, its noise-vocoded counterpart.

3.2.3 Linguistic tasks

In the linguistic tasks performed during fMRI and previously used by Moisala et al. (2015, 2016), Finnish semantically congruent and incongruent sentences were used as stimuli. The sentences were presented either auditorily (speech via headphones) or visually (text on a screen). Semantically congruent sentences were simple phrases about everyday subjects (e.g., “This morning I ate a bowl of cereal”). Incongruent sentences were created by taking a subset of the congruent sentences and changing the last word of the sentence to a semantically incongruent but syntactically plausible word (e.g., “This morning I ate a bowl of shoes”). In the reading task, the participants were to classify written sentences, and in the listening task, they were to classify spoken sentences, as congruent or incongruent by pressing a button under their right index or middle finger, respectively. In the distracted reading and listening conditions, each to-be-classified sentence was accompanied by a concurrent unrelated sentence delivered in the other modality, whereas in the undistracted reading and listening conditions, no sentences were presented in the other modality.

The written sentences were presented for 2.5 s. However, during the first 2 s, the last word was replaced with as many letters ‘x’ as there were letters in the last word that was revealed for the final 0.5 s. The spoken sentences had a duration of about 2.5 s. In the trials where both written and spoken sentences were presented, each spoken sentence was timed so that its last word began at the same time when the last word in the written sentence was revealed. After each sentence, there was a 1-s response window, during which a question mark on the screen and the participants were to give their answer by pressing the appropriate response button.

During fMRI, altogether 72 written sentences and 72 spoken sentences, both presented in blocks of 12 sentences, were to be classified by the participants as semantically congruent or incongruent. In half of the blocks, the target sentences were accompanied by distractor sentences in the other modality.

3.2.4 Flanker task

In the Flanker task, the participants’ task was to indicate the direction of a target arrow, that is, a left or right pointing arrow, by pressing the corresponding key, that is, left or right key. The target arrows were flanked by distractors, that is, two arrows on each side of the target. The distractor arrows either pointed in the same direction as the target (i.e., $\rightarrow\rightarrow\rightarrow\rightarrow\rightarrow$ or $\leftarrow\leftarrow\leftarrow\leftarrow\leftarrow$; congruent condition), or in the opposite direction (i.e., $\rightarrow\rightarrow\leftarrow\rightarrow\rightarrow$ or $\leftarrow\leftarrow\rightarrow\leftarrow\leftarrow$; incongruent condition). Thus, the participants were to indicate the direction of the target arrow while suppressing the direction of the distractors. In total 40 test items were administered. Half of the targets pointed to the left and the other half to the right, while in half of the trials, distractors pointed in the same direction as the target, and in the other half, they pointed to the opposite direction. After fixation, a test item appeared for 2500 ms, followed by a black screen that remained visible for 1000 ms during which the participants were to give their response. Reaction time (RT) and response accuracy were registered by the computer. An inverse efficiency score (accuracy divided by RT) was used as a performance measure. Before the actual task started, 12 trials were presented, where only one arrow pointing to the left or right was presented in the center of the screen (neutral condition). Responses from this neutral condition were used as an *individual* baseline for the analyses of data from the actual Flanker task.

3.2.5 n-back task

In the n-back task, two sequences of 20 colored images (e.g., a rocket, a sweater) were shown. For each image, the participants were to indicate whether the presented image was identical to the image presented 2 trials back by answering ‘yes’ or ‘no’ by pressing a response key (‘j’ for yes, ‘f’ for ‘no’). In each sequence, 30% of trials were target trials (i.e., the correct answer was ‘yes’). The first 3 trials of each sequence were always nontarget items. After fixation, each stimulus appeared for 3000 ms, followed by a black screen that remained visible for 1000 ms, during which the participants were to give their response. The next stimulus appeared after this 1000-ms response window. The performance measure was the accuracy of responses. To familiarize the participants with the task, a practice sequence of 20 items was presented before the actual task sequences from which the data was collected.

4 Results

4.1 Mathematical tasks

4.1.1 Performance

For the mathematical tasks performed during fMRI, a repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) with factors Task (Solve vs. Create vs. Select) and Distractor (dialogue+babble vs. its noise-vocoded counterpart) showed a significant effect of Task ($F(1.81,341.09) = 1017.67, p < .001$; Greenhouse-Geisser corrected degrees of freedom) and Distractor ($F(1,188) = 10.65, p < .01$). As seen in Figure 3, the participants gave less correct answers per the one-minute blocks in the Create task than in the Solve or Select task, and as expected, less correct answers at the presence of task-irrelevant dialogue plus babble than at the presence of its incomprehensible noise-vocoded version.

Figure 3. Performance in the mathematical tasks

Left: The participants gave less correct answers per one-minute blocks in the Create task than in the Solve or Select tasks. The black, blue, and yellow squares show the across-participant mean number of correct answers per block for the Solve, Create, and Select task, respectively. The error bars indicate standard errors of the mean (SEMs) and the grey circles depict the mean of correct answers per block for each participant and condition.

Right: The participants gave less correct answers per block at the presence of task-irrelevant dialogue plus babble than at the presence of its incomprehensible noise-vocoded counterpart (data combined across the three tasks). The red and green squares show the mean number of correct answers per block for the dialogue+babble distractor and its noise-vocoded counterpart, respectively. The error bars indicate SEMs and the grey circles the mean number of correct answers for each participant and condition.

To study effects of background variables on performance in the mathematical tasks, we ran an ANOVA with between-participant factors Sex, Age and SES and within-participant factors Task and Distractor (the effects of within-participant factors reported above are ignored here). This ANOVA showed significant effects of Age ($F(1,185) = 55.40, p < .001$) and SES ($F(1,185) = 4.40, p < .05$). As seen in Figure 4, the performance was better the older was the participant and the higher was the participant's SES. There was no significant difference in performance between the male and female participants ($F(1,185) = 0.03, p = 0.86$).

Figure 4. Effects of age and SES on performance in the mathematical tasks

Left: The participants gave more correct in the mathematical tasks (data combined across the Create, Solve, and Select tasks) the older they were at the time of the measurement. The grey circles indicate the means of correct answers per block for each participant and the blue line is a linear trend fitted to the data showing a positive association between performance and age.

Right: Performance in the mathematical tasks was better the higher was the participant's socio-economic status (SES). The red, green, and blue squares indicate the mean values for participants belonging to the highest SES group 1, second highest SES group 2, and third highest SES group 3, respectively. The black error bars indicate SEMs and the grey circles depict performance of individual participants. The SES group was defined based on participant's answer to the ySKILLS questionnaire. No participants belonged to the SES groups 4 or 5. In one participant, a missing SES value was replaced by the median SES value 2.

Finally, we conducted separate ANOVAs for the following ICT skills measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire: (1) technical and operational skills, (2) information, navigation and processing skills, (3) communication and interaction skills, (4) content creation and production skills; as well as for the amount of following online activities measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire: (1) Social media use, (2) overall internet use, (3) online learning, and (4) online gaming. In these ANOVAs, in addition to the studied skill or online activity, Sex, Age, and SES were used as between-participant factors and Task and Distractor as within-participant factors. Only statistically significant effects of the studied skill or activity and its significant interactions with the within-participant factors were of interest, but no significant effects were found in these ANOVAs (all p -values > 0.08).

4.1.2 Brain activity

A comparison of brain activity during the Solve and Create tasks with the Select task (included to control for the visual and motor processes during the tasks) showed enhanced activity in a wide network of cortical regions (Figure 5, red/orange/yellow areas on the top and middle rows) including areas in the frontal and parietal cortices and resembling the pattern of data observed previously in adults performing the same mathematical tasks (Ylinen et al., 2022), and in line with the emergence of fronto-parietal networks that are typically observed during the execution of mathematical tasks (Peters & De Smedt, 2018). Moreover, activity in many cortical regions was lower during the Solve and Create tasks than during the Select task (Figure 5, blue/cyan areas on the top and middle rows).

These areas included the visual and motor cortices, suggesting differences in visuo-motor activity between the quite mechanic Select task and the Solve/Create tasks demanding calculation in addition to visuo-motor processes. Moreover, activity in the auditory and speech processing areas of the superior temporal lobe was lower during the Solve and Create tasks than during the Select task, suggesting that during the Solve and Create tasks, processing of the distracting speech stimuli was actively suppressed. As seen in Figure 5 (bottom), the task-irrelevant dialogue+babble distractor activated especially auditory areas in the superior temporal cortex more strongly than its noise-vocoded counterpart (red/orange/yellow areas in Figure 5, bottom row), whereas activity in many areas activated by the mathematical tasks was attenuated by the presence of dialogue+babble distractor (blue/cyan areas in Figure 5, bottom row).

Figure 5. Brain activity during mathematical tasks

Top: Contrast between brain activity measured with fMRI during the Solve and Select tasks. The red areas were activated significantly more strongly during the Solve task and the blue/cyan areas during the Select task.
Middle: Contrast between brain activity during the Create and Select tasks. The red/orange/yellow areas were activated significantly more strongly during the Create task and the blue/cyan areas during the Select task.
Bottom: Contrast between conditions with distracting dialogue plus babble delivered via headphones and conditions with its incomprehensible noise-vocoded counterpart delivered via headphones (data combined across the Solve, Create and Select tasks). The red/orange/yellow areas were activated significantly more strongly in the conditions with dialogue+babble than in the conditions with its noise-vocoded counterpart, whereas blue/cyan areas showed an opposite effect.
 The data are shown on inflated cortical surfaces of the left and right hemisphere (the gyri are depicted in lighter grey and the sulci in darker grey).

Associations of brain activity during the mathematical tasks and ICT skills and activities measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire were studied with ANOVAs conducted separately for each skill and activity with Task (Solve, Create, Select) and Distractor (dialogue+babble, noise-vocoded speech) as within-participant factors. Only one significant association was observed: Higher content creation and production skills were associated with higher activity in a small area in the white matter of the parietal lobe (Figure 6). However, this is likely to be a random positive finding and it is presented with caution, since the functional significance and reliability of fMRI findings in the white matter is not generally accepted (Grajauskas et al., 2019; Mazerolle et al., 2020).

Figure 6. Association of content creation and production skills with possible activity in the parietal white matter of the left hemisphere during the mathematical tasks

Left: Significant association of content creation and production skills (measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire) and brain activity (measured with fMRI during the mathematical tasks) in the parietal white matter of the left hemisphere (the red/orange/yellow area). Brain activity was analyzed with an ANOVA, where effects of Sex, Age, and SES were controlled. A cluster p threshold of 0.05 and cluster forming $p < 0.001$ were used. The p-values were calculated using 5000 permutations and FWE-corrected (FWE referring to family-wise error rate).

Right: Mean fMRI signal change (in arbitrary units, AU) in the white matter area showing the significant association for participants achieving different scores on their content creation and production skills. The black dots indicate mean fMRI signal change in individual participants, the blue line shows a linear trend fitted to the data.

4.2 Linguistic tasks

4.2.1 Performance

In the linguistic tasks performed during fMRI, a repeated-measures ANOVA with factors Task (reading vs. listening), Semantic congruence (congruent vs. incongruent sentences), and Distractor (task-irrelevant sentence in the other modality present vs. absent) showed a significant effect of Distractor ($F(1,59) = 7.75, p < .01$). As shown by Figure 7, the participants classified target sentences more accurately as congruent or incongruent at the absence of a distractor sentence than at the presence of distractor.

To study effects of background variables on performance accuracy, we ran another ANOVA with between-participant factors Sex, SES, and Age and within-participant factors Task, Semantic congruence, and Distractor (the effects of within-participant factors reported above are ignored here). This ANOVA showed significant main effects of Sex ($F(1,56) = 8.30, p < .01$) and SES ($F(1,56) = 4.74, p < .05$). As seen in Figure 8, the female participants performed overall more accurately in the linguistic tasks than the male participants, and the performance was more accurate, the higher was the participant's SES.

Figure 7. Performance accuracy in the reading and listening tasks

During the reading task, the participants classified written sentences less accurately as congruent vs. incongruent at the presence than at the absence of spoken distractor sentences, and during the listening task, they classified spoken sentences less accurately at the presence than at the absence of written distractor sentences. The red and green squares indicate the mean performance accuracy (proportion of correct classifications) during the reading and listening tasks, the black error bars showing SEMs. The grey circles show performance accuracy of individual participants.

Figure 8. Sex, SES, and performance accuracy in the linguistic tasks

Left: Performance accuracy in the linguistic tasks (data for reading and listening combined) was higher in the female than in the male participants. The red and green squares indicate the mean performance accuracy for the females and males, respectively. The error bars show SEMs and the grey circles depict accuracy of individual participants.

Right: Performance accuracy was higher the higher was the participant's SES. The blue, green, and red squares show the mean values of participants in the highest SES group 1, the second SES group 2, and the third SES group 3, respectively. The SES group was defined based on participant's answer to the ySKILLS questionnaire. No participants belonged to the SES groups 4 or 5. In one participant, a missing SES value was replaced by the median SES value 2.

Finally, like for the data from the mathematical tasks, we conducted separate ANOVAs for the following ICT skills measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire: (1) technical and operational skills, (2) information, navigation and processing skills, (3) communication and interaction skills, (4) content creation and production skills; as well as for the amount of following online activities measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire: (1) Social media use, (2) overall internet use, (3) online learning, and (4) online gaming. In these ANOVAs, in addition to the studied skill or online activity, Sex, Age, and SES were used as between-participant factors and Task and Distractor as within-participant factors. From these ANOVAs, only significant effects of the skill/activity in focus and its interactions with the within-participant factors are reported here.

First, the communication and interaction skills had a significant interaction with semantic congruence ($F(1,55) = 10.38, p < .005$). As shown by Figure 9 (left), the participants scoring low on these skills classified congruent sentences as congruent more accurately than incongruent sentences as incongruent, whereas there was no such difference for those scoring high on these skills.

Figure 9. Communication and interaction skills and semantic language processing

There was a significant interaction of the communication and interaction skills with Semantic congruence: Participants scoring low on these skills classified semantically congruent sentences as congruent more accurately than semantically incongruent sentences as incongruent, but there was no such difference for those scoring high on this skill (data from the reading and listening tasks combined). The green and red dots indicate individual participants' accuracy in classifying the congruent and incongruent sentences, respectively, and the green and red lines depict linear trends fitted to the data for congruent and incongruent sentences, respectively.

Second, there was a significant 3-way interaction of the communication and interaction skills, Task (reading vs. listening), and Distractor (present vs. absent) ($F(1,55) = 6.59, p < .05$). As seen in Figure 10 (left), the higher the participants scored on these skills, the worse was their performance in the reading task, and the larger was the deteriorating effect of spoken distractor sentences on their performance accuracy. Also, in non-distracted trials of the listening task, participants' performance tended to be less accurate the higher they scored on the communication and interaction skills, whereas during the listening task, performance accuracy was less affected by the written distractor sentences for participants with higher communication and interaction skills and for these participants, the distractor effect was absent.

Third, there was also a significant 3-way interaction of the content creation and production skills, Task and Distractor ($F(1,55) = 5.13, p < .05$). As shown by Figure 10 (right), the interaction pattern was quite similar to the 3-way interaction of the communication and interaction skills, Task and Distractor.

Figure 10. Association of communication and interaction skills and content creation and production skills with performance in the linguistic tasks

Left: There was a significant 3-way interaction of the communication and interaction skills, Task and Distractor: The higher the participants scored on these skills, the worse was their classification performance during the reading task, and the stronger was deterioration of their performance caused by spoken distractor sentences. Even in non-distracted trials of the listening task, the participants' performance tended to be less accurate the higher was their score on these skills, but during the listening task, performance accuracy became better, and the distractor effect smaller, with was less affected by the written distractor sentences for participants with higher communication and interaction skills.

Right: There was also a significant 3-way interaction of the content creation and production skills, Task and Distractor: The higher the participants scored on these skills, the worse was their semantic classification performance in the reading and listening tasks, the stronger was the deteriorating effect of the spoken distractor sentences on their reading task performance, and the smaller was the deteriorating effect of written distractor sentences on their listening task performance, the latter distractor effect being absent for the highest scoring participants.

The green and red dots indicate individual participants' accuracy in classifying the sentences as congruent and at the presence or absence of distractor sentences, respectively, and the green and red lines depict linear trends fitted to the data for presence or absence of distractor sentences, respectively.

Fourth, there was a significant association of online gaming and performance accuracy in the linguistic tasks. In the ySKILLS questionnaire, amount of online gaming was studied on a 6-step scale (“In the past month, I played games on my computer or phone (1) never, (2) a few times, (3) at least every week, (4) daily or almost daily, (5) several times each day, (6) almost all the time”). Since only few participants got the score 1 or 6, we formed Gaming Score Groups 2, 3, 4, and 5: Group 1–2 ($n = 10$) consisted of those scoring 1 or 2, Group 3 ($n = 16$) included those scoring 3, Group 4 ($n = 21$) included those scoring 4, and Group 5–6 ($n = 13$) consisted of those scoring 5 or 6. An ANOVA with factors Group, Task, Semantic congruence, and Distractor (as well as Sex, Age, and SES) revealed a significant effect of online gaming on performance accuracy in the linguistic tasks ($F(3,53) = 4.32, p < .01$). As seen in Figure 11, performance accuracy increased gradually from Group 1–2 to Group 4 but then dropped markedly for Group 5–6.

Figure 11. Amount of online gaming and performance in the linguistic tasks

There was a significant association of the amount of online gaming with performance accuracy in the linguistic tasks (data from reading and listening combined): Accuracy increased gradually from Group 2 to Group 4 but then dropped for Group 5. Group 1–2 consisted of those who reported online gaming “never” or “a few times” in the last month, Group 3 included those who reported “at least every week”, Group 4 included those who reported “daily or almost daily”, and Group 5–6 consisted of those who reported “several times each day” or “almost all the time”. The black squares indicate the mean performance accuracy for each group and the error bars show SEMs. The grey circles depict accuracy of individual participants.

4.2.2 Brain activity

As shown by Figure 12 (top row), the reading and listening tasks activated large cortical networks including visual and auditory cortical areas, respectively, as well as several language processing areas. These brain activity patterns closely resembled those observed in adults in the same experimental paradigm (Moisala et al., 2015). As expected, these activations were largely wider in the left hemisphere than in the right hemisphere, reflecting the left-hemisphere dominance in linguistic processes. For both tasks, activity was also observed in the somatomotor areas of the left hemisphere due to the right-hand button presses in the semantic classification tasks.

As also shown by Figure 12 (bottom row) the spoken distractor sentences delivered during the reading task activated auditory cortical areas in both hemispheres and the written distractor sentences during the listening task activated the occipital and parietal visual processing predominantly in the left (language dominant) hemisphere, as well as in the premotor areas of the left hemisphere.

Figure 12. Brain activity during the reading and listening tasks

Top row, left: Contrast between the reading task (without spoken distractors) and rest blocks with no task and no written or spoken sentences. The red/yellow areas were activated more strongly during the reading task than during rest. **Top row, right:** Contrast between the listening task (without written distractor sentences) and the rest condition. The data are shown on inflated cortical surfaces of the left and right hemisphere. The red/yellow areas were activated more strongly during the listening task than during rest. **Bottom row, left:** Contrast between the reading task with the spoken distractor sentences and the reading task without the spoken distractor sentences revealing the brain areas (red/yellow) activated by the spoken distractor sentences. **Bottom row, right:** Contrast between the listening task with written distractor sentences and the listening task without the written distractor sentences revealing the brain areas (red/yellow) activated by the written distractor sentences.

Associations of brain activity during the mathematical tasks and ICT skills and activities measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire were studied with ANOVAs conducted separately for each skill and activity with Task (Solve, Create, Select) and Distractor (dialogue+babble, noise-vocoded speech) as within-participant factors. Only one significant association was observed: Higher information, navigation, and processing skills were associated with higher activity in the anterior insula of the left hemisphere (Figure 13). Previous studies have implicated this brain area in linguistic processing (Ardilla et al., 2014; Oh et al., 2014). However, due to the lack of association of information, navigation, and processing skills with performance in the linguistic tasks, it is not possible to conclude whether a positive association between these skills and activity in the left anterior insula reflects more efficient or more effortful linguistic processing in those with higher self-reported information, navigation, and processing skills.

Figure 13. Association of brain activity and information, navigation, and processing skills

Left: Significant association of information, navigation, and processing skills (measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire) and activity (measured with fMRI) in the anterior insula of the left hemisphere shown on an inflated cortical surface to reveal the insula in the medial Sylvian fissure. Right: Mean fMRI signal change (in arbitrary units, AU) in the insular area showing the significant association for participants achieving different scores on their information, navigation, and processing skills. The black dots indicate mean signal change in individual participants and the blue line shows a linear trend fitted to the data. For details of the statistical analysis, see Figure 5.

4.3 Flanker and *n*-back tasks

In the Flanker task, which measured children's attention skills, participants showed the classic flanker effect with higher accuracy and reaction time (RT) in the congruent ($M_{acc} = 0.98$ ($SD_{acc} = 0.04$), $M_{RT} = 577$ ms ($SD_{RT} = 112$ ms)) vs. incongruent ($M_{acc} = 0.92$ ($SD_{acc} = 0.16$), $M_{RT} = 625$ ms ($SD_{RT} = 160$ ms)) trials (accuracy: $F(1,50) = 5.946$, $p = .018$; RT: $F(1,50) = 7.695$, $p < .001$). In the *n*-back task, children had an accuracy with a mean proportion correct of 0.75 ($SD = 0.08$).

We examined the associations between these cognitive tasks and the different dimensions of the ySKILLS questionnaire (Helsper et al, 2020). We also investigated the relations between these cognitive tasks and the various aspects of the ySKILLS performance tests (Helsper et al, 2020).

There was a negative association between the participants' attention skills and the amount of their online activities ($r = -.54$, $p < .01$) and sharing on social media ($r = -.45$, $p < .01$): Participants with lower attention skills had higher amounts of online activities and were sharing more on social media. There was also a negative association between participants working memory and their communication and interaction skills ($r = -.29$, $p < .05$) as well as a negative association between participants' working memory and their content creation and production skills. In both cases, participants with higher working memory showed lower scores on the ySKILLS questionnaire. This is somewhat in line with the data reported in Figure 9.

We also verified associations between these cognitive tasks and the different aspects of the ySKILLS performance tests (Helsper et al., 2020), although these associations should be interpreted with caution in view of the small sample of children who completed the performance tests ($n = 19$). Our data revealed a positive association between children's attention ($r = .58$, $p < .01$) and working memory ($r = .51$, $p < .05$) and their performance on the performance tests: the participants with higher attention and working memory skills showed higher ICT skills on the performance tests. This finding is in contrast with the negative association of working memory skills and self-reported communication and interaction skills reported above.

5 Discussion

Measurements of participants' performance and brain activity indicated the mathematical and linguistic tasks and distractors used in the fMRI measurements produced expected results. However, no associations were found between the participants' performance in the mathematical tasks and the ICT skills and activities measured with the ySKILLS questionnaire. It should be noted, that this result might be partly due to a limited variation in mathematical skills in the studied sample, as an average or better than average grade in school mathematics was used as an inclusion criterion.

However, there were some associations between ICT skills and activities and participants' performance in the linguistic tasks. First, the communication and interaction skills and the content creation and production skills had three-way interactions with Task (reading vs. listening), and Distractor (present vs. absent): The higher the participants scored on these skills, the worse was their semantic classification performance during distracted reading, non-distracted reading, and non-distracted listening, but for distracted listening, performance became even better with increasing communication and interaction skills leading to disappearance of distracting effect of task-irrelevant written sentences on classification of spoken sentences. These findings might be regarded as indicating a negative association of participants' communication, interaction, content creation, and production skills with their linguistic skills perhaps also leading to participants scoring high on these ICT skills being less likely to read the task-irrelevant sentences during the listening task. These findings are in line with the data from the present cognitive tasks, where participants with higher working memory had lower communication and interaction skills. Because the available data are only cross-sectional, the direction and causality of these associations remain an open issue, as it is impossible to determine from these data whether adolescents with lower reading and speech processing skills are prone to actively develop their ICT communication, interaction, content creation, and production skills, or whether they have developed these ICT skills at the expense of development of their linguistic skills. Moreover, it should be noted that the present linguistic tasks were performed during noisy fMRI and under time pressure and, therefore, may not reflect associations of the studied ICT skills with performance accuracy in everyday reading and listening situations. Finally, the finding of attenuating distraction of speech processing caused by task-irrelevant text with increasing communication, interaction, content creation, and production skills might also be interpreted as an enhanced ability to suppress task-irrelevant written information and concentrate on relevant speech information.

Second, the communication and interaction skills were also differentially associated with classification of congruent and incongruent sentences: the higher the participants scored on these ICT skills the more accurately they classified incongruent sentences as incongruent and the less accurately they classified congruent sentences as congruent. While this result is difficult to interpret, it suggests an association of linguistic skills and communication and interaction skills, like the afore-mentioned interactions between these skills and Task and Distractor factors in the linguistic tasks.

Third, there was a significant effect of participants' online gaming frequency and their performance in the linguistic tasks: Performance became gradually better with increasing amount of online gaming, in line with studies showing advantageous effects of gaming on cognitive skills in adolescents and young adults, including visual and auditory attention skills, as well as visuo-spatial and verbal working memory skills (Alho et al., 2022). However, performance accuracy dropped for those gaming excessively ("several times each day" or "almost all the time") suggesting that either detrimental effects of excessive gaming override the advantageous effects of moderate amounts of gaming or that adolescents with weaker language skills are more prone to excessive gaming, instead of other leisure activities, for example, reading. It should be noted that no association of online gaming frequency and performance in the mathematical tasks was observed in a larger sample of participants, suggesting that the association between gaming and performance in the semantic tasks indeed reflects association

between gaming frequency and language skills, as the present mathematical tasks, especially when performed at the presence of task-irrelevant speech, were presumably attentionally as demanding as the present distracted and non-distracted semantic sentence classification tasks .

There were also two significant associations of brain activity and ICT skills: Higher information, navigation, and processing skills were associated with higher activity in the anterior insula of the left hemisphere during the semantic tasks and higher content creation and production skills were associated with activity observed in the parietal white matter of the left hemisphere during the mathematical tasks.

Especially the insula in the left hemisphere has been implicated in speech production, but also with processing of spoken and written language (for meta-analyses of fMRI studies, see Ardilla et al., 2014; Oh et al., 2014). Therefore, the present association of information, navigation, and processing skills with activity in the left anterior insula presumably reflects an association of these ICT skills with linguistic brain functions. These ICT skills were not associated with activity in other brain areas more typically linked to language, for example, the areas showing enhanced activity in the reading and listening tasks in relation to a resting condition content creation and production skills (see Figure 12). Due to this, and due to the lack of significant association of information, navigation, and processing skills with performance in the present semantic tasks, it is not possible to interpret whether the higher activity in the left insula in participants with better information, navigation, and processing skills reflects, for example, more efficient or more effortful processing of language in the present semantic tasks. Whatever is the case, the lack of association of ICT skills and insular activity during the present mathematical tasks supports the interpretation that the association of insular activity and the information, navigation, and processing skills is related to linguistic brain functions.

The association of the content creation and production skills with activity observed in the parietal white matter of the left hemisphere during the mathematical tasks is even more problematic to interpret. First, these skills were not observed to be associated with performance in mathematical tasks. Second, the functional significance and reliability of fMRI findings in the white matter is not generally accepted (Grauskas et al., 2019; Mazerolle et al., 2020).

The current findings from the Flanker and n-back tasks provide some evidence for associations between adolescents' cognitive and ICT skills, but the associations differed depending on the way in which adolescents' ICT skills were measured. On one hand, there were negative associations between the participants' attention and working memory skills and their ICT skills as measured via the ySKILLS questionnaire: participants who obtained high scores on the questionnaire (especially, on the communication and interaction skills, content creation and production skills, amount of online activities and sharing social media online) had lower attention and working memory skills. Interestingly, different aspects of cognitive ability were differentially related with different dimensions of ICT skills. Attention skills were negatively related to the amount of online activities and sharing in social media. Working memory capacity, in turn, was negatively related to the communication and interaction skills, content creation and production skills, in line with the data from the linguistic task in the Finnish sample.

In a subgroup of Belgian participants, we also observed a positive association between cognitive skills and participant's performance on the ICT performance tests: those with higher attention and working memory skills showed higher performance on the ICT performance tests. Importantly, these data were only collected in 19 participants (this is the consequence of the fact that due to Covid-related restrictions, we had to run the study online). It is interesting to note that in this small sample, there was no association between the questionnaire data and the performance tests. This suggests that these two measures might tap into different aspects of ICT skills. Future studies should replicate these findings in larger samples.

6 Conclusions

The present studies examined associations of ICT skills and use with brain activity and performance during mathematical and linguistic tasks, as well as with attention and working memory skills. The data indicated no strong associations. Some weaker associations were observed, but these would require further replication. Given that the present data are cross-sectional, no strong causal implications can be drawn from the present data.

References

- Alho, K., Moisala, M., & Salmela-Aro, K. (2022). Effects of media multitasking and video gaming on cognitive functions and their neural bases in adolescents and young adults. *European Psychologist*, 27(2), 131–140. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1016-9040/a000477>
- Ardila, A., Bernal, B., & Rosselli, M. (2014). Participation of the insula in language revisited: A meta-analytic connectivity study. *Journal of Neurolinguistics*, 29(1), 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneuroling.2014.02.001>
- Arsalidou, M., & Taylor, M. J. (2011). Is $2+2=4$? Meta-analyses of brain areas needed for numbers and calculations. *NeuroImage*, 54(3), 2382–2393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2010.10.009>
- Baldo, J. V., & Dronkers, N. F. (2007). Neural correlates of arithmetic and language comprehension: A common substrate? *Neuropsychologia*, 45(2), 229–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropsychologia.2006.07.014>
- Davis, M. H., & Johnsrude, I. S. (2003). Hierarchical processing in spoken language comprehension. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 23(8), 3423–3431. <https://doi.org/10.1523/jneurosci.23-08-03423.2003>
- De Smedt, B. (2022). Individual differences in mathematical cognition: a Bert's eye view. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 46, 1011175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2022.101175>
- Eriksen, B. A., & Eriksen, C. W. (1974). Effect of noise letter upon the identification of a target letter in a nonsearch task. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 16(1), 143–149. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03203267>
- Grajauskas, L. A., Frizzell, T., Song, X., & D'Arcy, R. C. N. (2019). White matter fMRI activation cannot be treated as a nuisance regressor: Overcoming a historical blind spot. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 13, 1024. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2019.01024>
- Helsper, E. J., Schneider, L.S., van Deursen, A.J.A.M., & van Laar, E. (2020). *The youth Digital Skills Indicator: Report on the conceptualisation and development of the ySKILLS digital skills measure*. KU Leuven: ySKILLS.
- Mazerolle, E.L., Ohlhauser, L., Mayo, C.D., Sheriff, A., & Gawryluk, J.R. (2020), Evidence of underreporting of white matter fMRI activation. *Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging*, 51(5), 1596–1597. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmri.26952>
- McMullen, J., Brezovszky, B., Rodríguez-Aflecht, G., Pongsakdi, N., Hannula-Sormunen, M.M., & Lehtinen, E. (2016): Adaptive number knowledge: exploring the foundations of adaptivity with whole-number arithmetic. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 47, 172–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2016.02.007>
- Moisala, M., Salmela, V., Salo, E., Carlson, S., Vuontela, V., Salonen, O., & Alho, K. (2015). Brain activity during divided and selective attention to auditory and visual sentence comprehension tasks. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 9, 86. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2015.00086>
- Moisala, M., Salmela, V., Hietajärvi, L., Salo, E., Carlson, S., Salonen, O., Lonka, K., Hakkarainen, K., Salmela-Aro, K., & Alho, K. (2016). Media multitasking is associated with distractibility and increased prefrontal activity in adolescents and young adults. *NeuroImage*, 134, 113–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2016.04.011>
- Moisala, M., Salmela, V., Hietajärvi, L., Carlson, S., Vuontela, V., Lonka, K., Hakkarainen, K., Salmela-Aro, K., & Alho, K. (2017). Gaming is related to enhanced working memory

- performance and task-related cortical activity. *Brain Research*, 1655, 204–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres.2016.10.027>
- Oh, A., Duerden, E. G., & Pang, E. W. (2014). The role of the insula in speech and language processing. *Brain and Language*, 135(1), 96–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandl.2014.06.003>
- Pagani, L., Argentin, G., Gui, M., & Stanca, L. (2016). The impact of digital skills on educational outcomes: evidence from performance tests. *Educational Studies* 42(2), 137–162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2016.1148588>
- Pelegrina, S., Lechuga, M. T., García-Madruga, J. A., Elosúa, M. R., Macizo, P., Carreiras, M., ... Bajo, M. T. (2015). Normative data on the n-back task for children and young adolescents. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.01544>
- Peters, L. & De Smedt, B. (2018). Arithmetic in the developing brain: a review of brain imaging studies. *Developmental Cognitive Neuroscience*, 30, 265–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcn.2017.05.002>
- Salmela-Aro K., Alho, K., Järvinen, J., Salonen, V., Mannerström, R., Hietajärvi, L., Maksniemi, E., Puukko, K., Gale, J., Bossens, E., Ylinen, A., Wikman, P., Bellon, E., & De Smedt, B. (2022). *Report on the effects of ICT use on attention-related cognitive functions measured with ESM and fMRI. Focus on ESM and fMRI methods to measure effects of ICT skills and use on wellbeing and cognitive functions.* KU Leuven: ySKILLS.
- Sanbonmatsu, D. M., Strayer, D. L., Medeiros-Ward, N., & Watson, J. M. (2013). Who multitasks and why? Multi-tasking ability, perceived multi-tasking ability, impulsivity, and sensation seeking. *PLOS ONE*, 8, e54402. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0054402>
- Spiegel, J. A., Goodrich, J. M., Morris, B. M., Osborne, C. M., & Lonigan, C. J. (2021). Relations between executive functions and academic outcomes in elementary school children: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 147(4), 329-351. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000322>
- Ylinen, A., Hannula-Sormunen, M., McMullen, J., Lehtinen, E., Wikman, P., & Alho, K. (2022). Arithmetic problem solving during auditory distraction: An fMRI study. *A poster presented at ICON 2022, International Conference of Cognitive Neuroscience, Espoo, Finland, May 18–22, 2022.* Abstract #184. https://www.helsinki.fi/assets/drupal/s3fs-public/migrated-generic-group-long-pages/files/224404-icon2022_poster_abstracts.pdf

